

e-ISSN: 2584-2404

Volume 09 Issue 02 May-
Aug 2026

***Corresponding Author:
Sanika Kumbhar,**

*Student, Department of
Electrical Engineering, Dr.
D.Y. Patil Pratishthan's
College of Engineering,
Salokhenagar, Kolhapur,
Maharashtra, India*

Submission Date: Feb 23,
2026

Copyright Received Date:
Feb 27, 2026

A Review on Liquid Level Detection using Programmable Logic Controller

***Prof. Ravindra Lohar¹, Sanika Kumbhar^{2*}, Ganesh Patil³,
Siddesh Patil⁴, Gaurav Sawant⁵***

¹*Assistant Professor, Department of Electrical Engineering,
Dr. D.Y. Patil Pratishthan's College of Engineering,
Salokhenagar, Kolhapur, Maharashtra, India*

^{2,3,4,5}*Student, Department of Electrical Engineering, Dr.
D.Y. Patil Pratishthan's College of Engineering,
Salokhenagar, Kolhapur, Maharashtra, India*

ABSTRACT

In industries, effective liquid level control is essential. Sensors are used by PLC-based SISO and MIMO systems to provide precise automatic regulation, high dependability, and ease of use. [1] A PLC-VSD motor control system to lower energy and water loss in pumps is presented in the paper. VSDs improve efficiency and cost-effectiveness by adjusting motor speed based on demand, saving 15–20% energy and 10–15% water. [2] A Mitsubishi PLC with pressure sensors and Omron SCADA over Ethernet is equipped with a swarm optimization-based PID controller. It guarantees quick reaction times and little variation in the water level. [3] ESP32 and ESP are used in a low-cost smart water pump system for water level display and real-time local control. Without relying on the internet, it guarantees reliable, low-latency functioning. [4]

Keywords:- PLC, Level Control, Pumps, Automation

INTRODUCTION

Accurate liquid-level monitoring in industries is made possible by PLC-based automation. It improves process accuracy and dependability while lowering human error. extensively utilized for efficiency and safety in the food, chemical, wastewater, and oil and gas industries. [1] Energy-efficient control of water supply pumps is made possible by VSD with PLC.

By adjusting pump speed in response to demand, water and electricity waste are reduced. DOL, Star-Delta, and soft starts are examples of conventional motor starters that are less effective. [2] Precise water level management is provided by PSO- optimized PID controllers on PLC. Control precision and system

responsiveness are improved by real-time SCADA feedback. Overall stability is increased and oscillations are reduced with adaptive tuning. [3] Automated water level control systems guarantee dependable and effective water management; NOW allows for quick, local operation independent of the internet. Flexibility and performance are enhanced by modular sensors and controllers with user settings. [4]

METHODOLOGY

A PLC is used by the system to regulate the water level in an above tank. It has two modes of operation: automatic mode, where the pump starts at low water level and stops at high water level, and manual mode, where the user can start or stop the pump.

Fig.1:-Block Diagram of System

A switch in the source tank stops the pump from operating when there is not enough water, while two digital level switches in the above tank monitor the low and high levels. By processing these signals, the PLC manages the pump motor and keeps the water level within predetermined bounds. This configuration offers a straightforward and efficient automated water level control system level by preventing both overflow and dry- run. [1]

OVERVIEW

➤ **PLC Ladder Programming**

IEC 61131-3 states that PLCs provide a range of programming languages, including Function Block Diagram (FBD) and Ladder Diagram (LD). Industrial applications are where LD and FBD are most frequently utilized. With horizontal rungs for control logic and vertical rails for power, ladder diagrams mimic electrical circuits.

Because of this, PLC programming is simple to use and intuitive for automation jobs.

➤ **Flow Sensor**

In industrial processes, fluid flow rates are measured and tracked by flow sensors. Electromagnetic, ultrasonic, thermal, mass flow and differential pressure sensors are common varieties that work on various principles to provide precise flow data.

➤ **Level Sensor**

Level sensors, such as ultrasonic, float, radar, and capacitance sensors, are used to measure liquid or solid levels.

➤ **Working of Level Sensor**

Ultrasonic sensors employ sound waves, capacitance sensors detect the

presence of materials, optical sensors use light, radar sensors use waves, and float sensors move with the liquid to monitor levels.

IMPLEMENTATION

PLCs use digital signals (0 and 1) to receive data from sensors and control devices. This makes the system fast, reliable, and easy to set up.

The Coupled Tank System

The paper describes a PLC-based coupled tank system to control liquid levels and prevent overflow in industries. It uses MIMO (two tanks, two pumps, two sensors) and SISO setups to monitor and regulate water levels accurately, with system behavior affected by tank levels and valve openings [1]

WORKING PRINCIPLE OF VARIABLE SPEED DRIVE (VSD)

Fig.2:-Basic Components of electronic circuit for VSD

Motor speed is managed using Variable Speed Drives (VSDs), sometimes known as ASDs or VFDs. First, they use a rectifier to convert the incoming AC electricity to DC. After that, a circuit known as the DC link smoothes the DC.

The inverter then uses switches like IGBTs to convert the DC back to AC at the required voltage and frequency. By transmitting signals, a control unit oversees everything and makes sure the system operates as needed.

OPERATING PRINCIPLES OF A VSD

The VSD adjust an induction motor's speed compliance with the synchronous speed equation by altering the frequency of the voltage provide to the motor. Devices like pumps and fans can work at different speeds by adjusting the motor

speed, which can change the flow rate, head, and power. To put it another way, precisely changing the input frequency enables control over the operation of the motor and related equipment. The variable speed pump's working principle is shown in Fig.3

Fig.3:- Operating Graph of pump adjusted speed relative to the normal system

Pumps that don't have a VSD need valves to regulate flow, which raises system pressure and loses energy. By using a VSD, the pump minimizes water loss, lowers pressure, and saves energy by adjusting its speed to match the necessary flow. The VSD can adjust pumping volume in response to demand when paired with a PLC, maximizing water and electricity efficiency.

SIMULATION OF A VARIABLE SPEED DRIVE SYSTEM

Since the motor used to operate a pump run at 100% rpm, it is possible to lower electricity costs and water loss when there is little demand for water at night and the water supply is only available 30-50% of the time during the day. The simulation's system diagram is displayed in below diagrams [2]

Fig.4:-System Diagram of water pump system

PID control system as illustrated as shown in figures (a), (b) and (c)

Fig.5:-PID- Based Control System

WATER LEVEL SYSTEM

In this work, an ultrasonic sensor checks the water level and provides feedback to the PLC for closed-loop control, while a PWM signal converts a DC pump into 0–24 V DC. Armature current determines motor torque, while back EMF

determines speed. The DC motor transfer function is derived using Kirchhoff's and Newton's principles, enabling the regulation of pump speed and, consequently, water flow. The water level is monitored and remotely controlled via SCADA.

Fig.6:- Schematic Diagram of Water Level Control System

Figure 6 displays the tank and SCADA setup together with a set of input and output data related to the water level. An

ultrasonic sensor detects the water level, and the motor voltage regulate the input flow.

Fig.7:-SCADA and hardware setup of water tank system

Fig 7. Figure depicts the full water level control mechanism. The input voltage of the pump is represented by v , the water level by h , the input flow rate by Q_i , and

the output voltage by y . pump input graphs, which are thought to be linear, link the input voltage, v , and the pump flow rate, Q_i .

Fig.8:-Schematic Diagram of the overall system

The same applies to the liquid water level sensor graphs shown in Figure 8

Fig.9:-Characteristic of Pump and level sensor

The gains of the pump and sensor are denoted by K_{pump} and K_{sensor} . Both pump and sensor properties affect the system gain is time constant if the system that influence the pace of response.

ARCHITECTURE OF PLC-BASED WATER LEVEL CONTROL SYSTEM

Figure 9 display the electrical circuit if the water level system and the closed loop analog signal inside the plc controller.

Fig.10:-Block Diagram and Components of equivalence circuit

The water level system consists of a pumping motor with two control settings and an operating voltage of 24 VDC. The water level is measured and detected by the ultrasonic sensor, which has a measuring range of 0 to 300 mm. A mitsubishi PLC processor controls the water level.

CONTROLLER ALGORITHM

A. Convectional PID Controller

Because of its reliability and ease of use, PID is frequently employed in control systems. It uses proportional, integral, and derivative operations to maintain motor controlled water levels. PID is closed - loop system that constantly modifies itself

in response to input. PSO stands for Particle Swam Optimization Algorithm.

B. Particle Swarm Optimization (PSO) Algorithm

A group of random particles is used in the particle Swarm optimization (PSO) technique to find the optimal solution. Particles change their position and speed across generations determine the optimal solution. This method is straightforward, effective, and frequently employed in control and optimization problems.

C.PID Controller Based On PSO

The swarm-optimized PID Controller presented in this section uses PSO to find

the ideal PID gains (k_p , k_i , and k_d) for the water level system. Using a performance index, the approach seeks to reduce the system error. This method uses 50 repetitions of 20 random particles, and MATLAB is utilized to determine the optimal controller settings and compute the performance index. [3]

The water pump is controlled by the system via ESP32 boards. An ultrasonic sensor measures the water level and wirelessly communicates the data. The OLED display indicates the current water level, and users can change tank size and limitations via a web page. It was verified for accuracy and stability and can operate both manually and automatically.

IMPLEMENTATION

Here in Fig 2, the connection of the circuit is shown with all the sensor modules, relay module, OLED display, buzzer and the brain of this system; microcontroller ESP32

Using an ultrasonic signal, the ultrasonic sensor in this system (Fig.3) determines the water level and transmit the data to the microcontroller. the water level is below the threshold level, then the pump is kept on if not, the pump is automatically off using the relay. In Fig 4, the sensor is sensed the water level is medium the and so the pump is still kept on.

The configuration shown in Fig. 5 shows a compact enclosure housing the main components of the automated water pump control system. Real-time system status can be seen on an OLED display

thanks to a cutout on the front. For manual control and feedback, an LED indicator and a red push button are installed outside.

PROPOSED MODULAR TOPOLOGY FOR INDUSTRIAL USAGE

The developed system can be used in industry by using modular topology where a central ESP32 will control the whole

operation of all the pumps by connecting with the local ESP32 controllers connected with each pump.

SYSTEM ARCHITECTURE

System architecture of the water pump system [4]

Module	Description
Sensor Module	ESP32 with HC-SR04 ultrasonic sensor for distance-based water level monitoring
Controller Module	ESP32 with relay switch for pump actuation and manual push-button override
Wireless Communication	ESP-NOW protocol (local, peer-to-peer, no router/internet required)
User Interaction	Manual button and mobile interface (Bluetooth/Web App support)
Pump Logic	Threshold-based activation/deactivation based on sensed water level
Power Requirements	5V DC (ESP32), 230V AC (relay-controlled pump)
Deployment	Weatherproof enclosure for outdoor/residential use
Operational Range	Up to 200 meters (line-of-sight ESP-NOW communication)

CONCLUSION

PLC makes it simple and safe to monitor and regulate tank water levels. Correct readings are obtained by selecting the appropriate sensor and understanding how it operates. The system is more dependable and automatic thanks to basic ladder logic. [1] This essay describes the control of a pump motor using VSD and PLC. Approximately 1,314 kWh of electricity are saved daily thanks to the technology. Additionally, it lowers daily water loss by about 2,788 cubic meters. [2]

The objective is to use PLC and SCADA to design a water level control system. PID controller gains are set using PSO, and a gain scheduling technique is evaluated. The adaptive strategy outperforms the regular approach in terms of response time and volatility, according to the results. This paper shows a low-cost smart water pump using ESP-NOW for fast offline control. It works well without internet and is useful for homes, farms, and small industries. Future plans include adding more sensors and saving data for better water management. [4]

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